

Pathos

Open Science Impact Pathways

Deliverable D1.3

Key Impact Pathways for the open science framework

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Table 1: Document Revision History

Table of Contents

Disclaimer	5
Abbreviations	6
Executive Summary	7
1. Introduction.....	9
2. Approach	10
3. Data collection and analysis	13
3.1. Sources	13
3.2. Coding of information.....	16
3.3. Data summary	19
3.4. Initial mapping.....	21
3.5. Recasting and explication of assumptions.....	23
4. Results.....	24
4.1. Pathway 1 (Citizen Science).....	25
4.2. Pathway 2 (Open Access).....	29
4.3. Pathway 3 (Impact on climate and environment)	33
5. Impact pathways and causality	36
6. Lessons learnt and next steps	38
6.1. Lessons learnt.....	38
6.2. Next steps.....	39
References.....	41
Annex I: Updated data extraction fiche	46
Annex II: Proposed Key Impact Pathway Fiche	47

List of Tables

Table 1: Document Revision History	2
Table 2 Charting table from scoping review	14
Table 3 Definitions of individual steps.....	15
Table 4 Data extraction fiche	16
Table 5 Codes for activities: Open Science areas	17
Table 6 Codes for outcomes and impacts.....	18
Table 7 Inclusion of sources from scoping review	19
Table 8 Impact code occurrence.....	20
Table 9 Overview of screened and unscreened literature	40
Table 10 Proposed updates for data extraction fiche	40

List of Figures

Figure 1 Role of the present report in PathOS.....	12
Figure 2 Depiction of individual steps.....	17
Figure 3 Visualisation of all connections in the sampled data.....	22
Figure 4 Initial mapping of Citizen Science impact chain	25
Figure 5 Pathway for Citizen Science (Draft)	27
Figure 6 Initial mapping of Open Access impact chain.....	30
Figure 7 Pathway for Open Access (Draft).....	31
Figure 8 Initial mapping of effects leading to climate/environmental impact.....	34
Figure 9 Pathway for Impact on Climate and Environment (draft)	35

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Abbreviations

COVID-19	Coronavirus Disease
CS	Citizen Science
D	Deliverable
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
ID	Identifier
IPR	Intellectual Property Right
KIP	Key Impact Pathway
OA	Open Access
OS	Open Science
OSTP	White House Office of Science and Technology Policy
PathOS	Open Science Impact Pathways (Horizon Europe Project)
SDG	Sustainable Development Goal
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization

Executive Summary

Open Science is an umbrella term for a variety of different practices in public and private research, including Open Access to research publications, Open and FAIR Data, Citizen Science, Open Peer Review, Open Software, and others. With the growing salience of these practices at international level, for example through the UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science in 2021 (UNESCO, 2021). The PathOS project has as its high-level aim to systematize knowledge about the effects and the economic, societal, and academic impacts of Open Science.

This report explores the impacts of Open Science (OS) practices with the scope of a proof-of-concept study using the impact pathway concept described in PathOS D1.1 (Dekker et al., 2023). Based on previous data collected by PathOS, particularly from the scoping review by Klebel et al. (2024) and empirical case studies conducted by Cole et al. (2023), this report customizes, tests, and validates the Key Impact Pathway (KIP) approach in the context of Open Science. The approach utilises evaluation methods and concepts, particularly identifying impact chains (from activities to the creation of outputs, outcomes, and impacts) and collects and codes information from a set of 40+ sources.

The resulting information is used to generate high-level impact chains, displayed as intervention logics, of Open Science practices. Three such preliminary pathways indicating the impacts of different Open Science activities are identified in the report: 1) Citizen Science, 2) Open Access pathway, 3) Impacts on climate and environment. These were selected based on the availability of relevant evidence:

- A *Citizen Science pathway* was constructed based on the selection of ‘citizen science’ using a “downstream analysis” - starting from intervention and moving downstream to impacts. The pathway illustrates how citizen science interventions correlate with certain impacts such as ‘trust’ stemming from the outcome of engagement of citizens in citizen science projects.
- An *Open Access pathway* was likewise constructed through a “downstream” analysis and provides an initial view how availability of open access publication’s (output) relates to aspects such as novelty (outcome), quality (impact), reproducibility (Impact).
- *Impacts of Open Science on climate and environment* were identified through an “Upstream analysis” – starting from impact and moving upstream to relevant interventions. The approach tested whether selecting a given impact would yield an overview of the individual steps and effects leading to this type of impact. The findings illustrate the important mediating factor of policy and governance, which can be affected by a broad range of societal aspects.

This deliverable set out as a proof-of-concept of the applicability of the KIPs framework for Open Science and the results indicate that that the approach works in principle and can be

scaled up, allowing the identification of additional pathways and the refinement of the existing ones. Both tracing the effects of different Open Science interventions up to the impact stage (“downstream analysis”) and identifying the activities that may create certain academic, societal, and economic impacts (“upstream analysis”) are feasible.

The next steps involve several actions within the PathOS project. The evidence base will be expanded by integrating more documents and sources, with a careful selection and coverage of topics, with an updated data extraction template. The remaining PathOS case studies will be integrated as well. Efforts will be made to refine the representations and reporting of impact pathways. Focus will be on enhanced contextual explanations and explicating assumption, including their limitations and broader socio-economic contexts.

This deliverable will be updated by June 2025.

1. Introduction

Open Science is an umbrella term for a variety of different practices in public and private research, including Open Access to research publications, open and FAIR data, citizen science, open peer review, open software, and others. With the growing salience of these practices at international level, for example through the UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science in 2021 (UNESCO, 2021), and its integration into funding programmes and requirements worldwide (OSTP, 2022; European Commission, 2021a), there is also increasing attention to the impact(s) these practices are intended to create.

The *PathOS – Open Science Impact Pathways* project (<http://pathos-project.eu>) has as its high-level aim to systematize knowledge about exactly these impacts of Open Science. It provides conceptual frameworks (Dekker et al. 2023), indicators (Grypari et al. 2023)¹, case studies (Cole et al. 2023), and a scoping review of evidence (Klebel et al. 2023; Cole et al. 2024). These tools are intended to assist stakeholders, such as researchers, institutions, funders, and policymakers, to better understand the state-of-the-art on impacts of Open Science and to conceptualise and design policy and research strategies based on evidence.

A specific challenge so far identified by PathOS is the availability of evidence. A large-scale scoping review of existing academic and other literature (Klebel et al. 2023; Cole et al. 2024) conducted by the project showed that, depending on the area of Open Science, evidence for impact is lacking. Additional conceptual work by the project has also explored the challenges in attributing causal effects to practices of Open Science (Klebel and Traag, 2024). A key ambition of PathOS is therefore to better understand what type of impacts in the academic, economic, and societal realm can be proven to be affected by Open Science activities.

In this endeavour and this report specifically, the project pays specific attention to go beyond isolated notions of impacts. It conceptualises Open Science impacts through the lens of impact pathways, a tool used to design and evaluate policy programmes, projects, and other types of interventions originally developed by Rabl & Peuportier (1995). In the EU, the concept has been further developed to identify, for example, environmental impacts of research and innovation policy (Miedzinski et al, 2013).

With this report, we aim to build upon the PathOS findings so far and to provide a structured investigation of the existing evidence along through the lens of impact chains from activity to output to outcome to impact. The primary objective of this deliverable is therefore to test and validate an approach that was develop to identify Key Impact Pathways (KIPs) of Open Science. It does so by applying the step-by-step method described in PathOS D1.1 (Dekker et al. 2023) to a subset of the collected evidence. Specifically, the approach used for this report involves

¹ See the online version at <https://handbook.pathos-project.eu>

revisiting the data underlying scoping review (Klebel et al. 2024) and empirical case studies (Cole et al. 2023) should be understood as a proof-of-concept for the further work of PathOS. The approach and pathways presented throughout the report are not final results but stepping stones for the PathOS team to better describe the effects stemming from Open Science practices. It seeks to inform the refinement of methods and activities within PathOS. As such, a secondary objective is to inspire follow-up research. Considering the noted limitations with the availability of causal evidence in the scoping review, a secondary objective is also to nurture more debate and conceptual thinking about Open Science practices and their impacts beyond the PathOS consortium, as well as engagement with impact thinking across stakeholders.

The report is structured as follows. Section 2 briefly describes the conceptual background, in particular the Key Impact Pathway approach and the scope of the work done in preparing the deliverable. Section 3 presents the practical approach employed for this report. Section 4 presents initial pathways for three areas, namely Citizen Science, Open Access, as well as selected environmental/climate impacts. Section 5 briefly discusses how PathOS and the chosen approach relate to causal evidence for impacts of Open Science. Section 6 presents major the lessons learnt and next steps for the PathOS project.

2. Approach

This deliverable follows the approach described in a previous deliverable of the PathOS project (Dekker et al. 2023). The approach borrows concepts usually used in the context of evaluation, in particular the concept of an intervention logic (of a programme, policy, etc.). Such intervention logic models (or impact chain model) aim to (re)construct the internal intervention logic of the staff designing the intervention while structuring the intervention in logical sequence from activities to the creation of outputs, outcomes, and impacts.

For this purpose, the PathOS project has adopted commonly used definitions for the concepts used throughout the report (Dekker et al. 2023). Impacts are defined by PathOS as “long-lasting, elementary and wide-spread change that affect different segments of society, economy, and academia, and therefore the environment in general” (ibid.). For key impact pathways (KIPs) PathOS applies the definition of “the most important or relevant pathways” (ibid.) to achieve impact.

The approach proposed by PathOS applies a stepwise approach originated from other methods to derive intervention logic diagrams from information about complex systems. This method, which follows an iterative process based on data collection, recasting, and explicating underlying assumptions, permits “upstream” and “downstream” analysis of the data (Wilkinson et al., 2021). Wilkinson et al. (2021) do so in two main steps. First, a system map is created, in their case through a participatory process, with the intention to develop a holistic picture of contextual factors, positive and negative impacts, feedback loops, and other levers. Second, the

map is recast into a Theory of Change, by developing a “logical sequence’ from input to outcome” (ibid, p87). Here, activities, inputs, and key assumptions and uncertainties are also explicated.

Intervention logics are usually a practitioners’ tools to design policies, programmes, projects, and other interventions, and to study and evaluate them against their impact and other criteria such as effectiveness, efficiency, coherence and relevance. Their main purpose is to explicate the assumptions about causal effect chains to reach a specific objective through an intervention. Commonly used, for example in the context of the EU Better Regulation Guidelines (European Commission, 2021b), their development is closely tied to the use of qualitative and quantitative indicators for each element of the intervention logic. Therefore, they should consider the possibility to collect evidence for causal effects at each step.

Intervention logics appear as displaying linear effects from specific interventions to population-level impacts. With each step from intervention to impact, the size and strength of the effect will be more difficult to capture and verify. In previous reports, we called this the “dilution” of effects (Dekker et al., 2023). In practice, impacts are challenging to measure and confirm.

In the approach followed for this report, we therefore adapted the approach in three steps. First, data is collected through identification of impact chains from activity to output, outcome and impact. This step is largely based on the available evidence (literature, case studies) collected for the scoping review. It includes the coding of activities, outputs, outcomes, and impacts to different societal, academic, economic effects. A key difference to Wilkinson et al. (2021) is that the approach does not employ participatory system mapping but is based on secondary data analysis.

In the second step, based on this cumulation of evidence, the impact chains emanating from specific interventions (i.e., Open Science practices) are isolated and displayed visually. These are then recast into initial impact chains with a logical sequence. With this, we aimed to identify the range of impacts chains resulting from these more detailed interventions. In this step, an iterative and participatory element is introduced through involvement of the wider project team discussing the identified sequences and through validation with stakeholders. The usage of the codes assigned in step one, which are aligned with further project work, this step also allows linking the results to the PathOS indicator handbook and other results.

In the third step we enriched the identified causal chains with more detailed contextual information, articulating underlying assumptions, and other PathOS results. This is an important step to explain the context of each identified pathway, including the conditions that are necessary to give rise to specific effects. In this way, we render the identified pathways a more useful tool for readers and stakeholders.

It must be acknowledged that the described approach diverges from the usual application of intervention logics for an ex-post evaluation of past actions. For instance, an ex-post evaluation

should be conducted against the initial programme objectives and chosen indicators at every stage, including the inputs provided, such as funding, personnel, legislative reforms etc. With the evidence collected for PathOS being based on a post hoc selection and coding of findings for impacts, often without link to specific inputs, the direct usability for such ex-post assessments is limited.

In addition, a key difference lies in the usage of the term *key impact pathway* by PathOS. Indeed, the results presented later in Section 4 are much closer to linear intervention logics or theories of change. They are simplified representations of effects, with specific focus on the chain of effects stemming from individual interventions. It is possible to understand such impact chains as an *adaptation of structural causal models* (see Klebel and Traag, 2024) maybe more familiar to academic readers. Such models provide a visual representation of causal links, verified by evidence, but “not whether that effect is linear, exponential or an ‘interaction’ with some other effects” (Klebel and Traag, 2024, p. 2). Such models provide structural assumptions about effect chains of Open Science practices but should not be used as predictive tools. It is therefore crucial to explain the causal assumptions and limitations of the final pathways through the third step.

Considering the chosen approach and the evidence they incorporate, the pathways developed in PathOS should be mainly treated as tools that help stakeholders *access and navigate the found evidence* for effects and impacts of Open Science practices. They are not an attempt to prove that any Open Science practice will always create the exact same effects identified by the research done in PathOS, as this is necessarily depending on contextual conditions, inputs and other factors. Interpreted from the other end, that is the type of impact, they should also be understood as devices that help identify possible interventions. Their use is therefore intended for forward-looking programme or project design.

Figure 1 Role of the present report in PathOS

The purpose of the work underlying this deliverable was to test the stepwise approach outlined above with data from diverse sources and provide learnings for future work (see Figure 1). Following the formulation of the conceptual basis with PathOS D1.1, the report can be understood as the proof of concept of the method for the further identification of KIPs based on the same method. The potential of integrating other outputs of PathOS into a single framework is considered. This concerns specifically the results from the work on the remaining case studies, the development of different indicators, and the contextual knowledge developed through the scoping review. As such, the experiences gained from conducting this work also aim to inform concrete next steps of the PathOS project for future deliverables. This concerns specifically how to select and encode the remaining documents and other evidence to be included, how to visualise the results and add contextual information, and the pathways undergoing special scrutiny, based on project and stakeholder input.

3. Data collection and analysis

3.1. Sources

To be able to implement the approach described in section 2, suitable data had to be selected. We utilised the collective effort of the project partners, their different deliverables and ongoing works. In particular, the literature scoping exercise and case studies were used as data sources.

Literature as information source

In previous work, the PathOS project systematically identified over 30,000 records and through further selection, identified 479 relevant academic articles and other types of literature which contained information on impacts of Open Science. These documents were categorized on the basis of impact area into academia (311 documents), society (155 documents), and the economy (13 documents) (see Klebel et al. 2024). The list of documents has been made available online in the form of a Zotero library.² Project partners had analysed the publications and integrated systematically information in a charting table for each included document (see Table 2).

As described in more detail in PathOS D1.2 (Klebel et al. 2024), the identified 479 documents provided initial results on the distribution of impacts and the availability of evidence. Areas such as Citizen Science and Open Access yielded large numbers with evidence for impacts on academia and society while other Open Science related areas and impact areas were much less evident.

² Thomas Klebel, Nicki Lisa Cole, Lena Tsipouri, Eva Kormann, Istvan Karasz, Sofia Liarti, Lennart Stoy, Vincent Traag, Silvia Vignetti, Alkis Pitelis, Ioanna Grypari, Simon Apartis, & Tony Ross-Hellauer. (2023). Data from "PathOS - D1.2 Scoping Review of Open Science Impact" (v1.1) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7969951>

Since the objective of the deliverable is to serve as a proof-of-concept, the documents covering Citizen Science and Open Access were subsequently selected to test the approach in these areas. The data basis for the analysis in this report included 30 documents on the academic impact of Citizen Science, 30 documents on the societal impacts of Citizen Science, and a further 27 documents on the academic impacts of Open Access. In total, 87 individual documents were included.

Table 2 Charting table from scoping review

Data chart	Description
Author	Name of author/s
Publication year	Year that the article was published
Title	Title of the study
Abstract	Abstract of the study
OS type	Open Access, Open/FAIR Data, Open Methods, Citizen Science, Open Evaluation, Open Science General
Publication type	Journal, website, conference, etc.
DOI/URL	Unique identifier
Exclusion	Out of scope, non-English, duplicate
Justification	If a study was deemed to be out of scope, a justification had to be provided.
Relevance to which aspect of impact	<p>Academic: (Provisional list: Quality, Citations, Integrity, Equity, Collaboration, Trust, Efficiency, Productivity, Reuse)</p> <p>Societal: (Provisional list: Engagement, Participation, Education, Trust, Policy, Sustainable development goals, Gender, Diversity, Health, Climate/Environment, COVID-19, Equity, Empowerment)</p> <p>Economic: (Provisional list: Economic impact, Financial/monetary impact, Costs, Cost-Benefit Analysis, Input-output, Return on investment, Patenting, Innovation, Productivity, Saving)</p>
Study details and design (if applicable)	Type of study, empirical or review, etc. Notes on methods used in study (whether qualitative or quantitative, which population demographics studied, etc.)
Types of data sources included	Detail the data sources
Study aims	Overview of the main objectives of the study
Key findings	Noteworthy results of the study that contribute to the scoping review question(s)
Coverage	Optional field to note any relevant information about the level of coverage of the study, e.g., only specific countries, disciplines, demographics covered
Confidence assessment	Optional field to note any concerns about reliability/generalisability of findings (e.g., conflict of interest, potential biases, small sample sizes, or other methodological issues) within the study

The data extraction for this task commenced with the initial screening of the information for the 87 articles included in the PathOS scoping review indicated above. The prior collected information, in particular the fields summarising study details, study aims, key findings, as well as the abstract and full text enabled the team to identify relevant academic publications for the scope of this deliverable. Data was extracted when the document indicated an individual intervention logic, which was also supported by data evidence. Specifically, the documents were screened for a description of concrete *activities*, the description of *outputs* of these activities, as well as the description of *outcomes* and *impacts*. If no such information could be extracted, decided upon discussion across the study team, documents were excluded. The definitions for each step used by PathOS are shown in Table 3 below.

Table 3 Definitions of individual steps

Step	Definition
Activity	Actions that lead to the (desired) outputs.
Output	Directly related measurable effects of activities that can be controlled by the initiators of the intervention.
Outcome	The likely or achieved short-term and medium-term effects of the outputs (mostly measurable social, economic and academic changes). There is only limited (or no) control by the intervention initiator.
Impact	Long-lasting, elementary and wide-spread change that affects different segments of society, economy, and academia, and therefore the environment in general. Impacts can be caused by multiple stakeholder interventions, and multiple stakeholders can be affected. Impacts can be direct or indirect, intended or unintended, relate to behavioural and/or systemic changes.

Deliverable 1.2 as information source

Building on the literature analysis, the project has written an extensive scoping review (PathOS D1.2) summarising the overarching findings from the screened literature. The present deliverables is testing the methods for the construction of impact pathways and thus a Chapter 4.2 of D1.2 was included as information source and subsequently treated as an information source similar to the individual papers outlined above. Chapter 4.2 of D1.2 specifically summarises key findings from 137 papers on Citizen Science.

The choice to include this chapter of a previous PathOS report next to the 87 papers outlined in the sub-section above was twofold. First, as a proof-of-concept testing the approach, trying the charting of different sources was deemed an important exercise. Second, the scoping review already identified evidence for impact of Citizen Science which could potentially be used as information for the construction of the impact pathways covering aspects such as:

- Education and Awareness,
- Climate and Environment,
- Social Engagement,

- Policy and Governance,
- Health, Empowerment and Equity,
- Trust and Attitudes toward Science.

Case studies as data source

PathOS also includes six case studies of different Open Science initiatives, which are reported in PathOS D3.1 (Cole et al. 2023). In order to test the potential of case studies as input source and, as second objective, to better understand how to further develop the case studies within PathOS, the so-far most advanced case study was selected. We thus examined the ELIXIR case study, designed to investigate the economic impacts of an ELIXIR (open) resource. In this specific case study, the team had already developed an intervention logic and depicted the various components showing activities, outputs, outcome, impacts. This choice constituted a form of convenience sampling, adopted to make the research process testing our approach more efficient.

3.2. Coding of information

Since the objective of this deliverable is to delineate Key Impact Pathways based on evidence collected from diverse sources, we scrutinized the selected sources (87 documents) with the aim of uncovering individual impact chains.

For the collection and analysis of data, the project developed a data extraction fiche (Table 4) to process information in a more standardised way, in particular to support the next step. Data in this context means qualitative information about the source document and the identified steps in the impact chains. As highlighted in PathOS D1.1, a systematic analysis relies on templates and protocols supporting a systematic analysis. In our case, this helped assigning the collected information to the impact chain components of activity, output, outcome, and impact, as well as further assigning them to impact areas (see Dekker et al. 2023, p. 28).

In addition, the data extraction fiche also permits the tracking of each coded information by step, its source information, the text extract etc. This also provides transparency, facilitating reproduction of the work undertaken by the study team.

Table 4 Data extraction fiche

Variable	Description
Source	Name of case study OR ID of paper OR relevant D1.2 chapter
Type of source	Case study OR scoping review OR literature
When	Date of extraction into fiche
Who	Name or initials of researcher doing the coding
Quote/text	Copy of relevant text (e.g., "key findings" from data charting), where feasible
Description of logic	Short description of intervention logic (optional)

Variable	Description
Step (Cause)	Select one: Activity, Output, Outcome, short-term Impact, Long-term impact
Type (Cause)	Select one: from coding table or add additional one
Step (Effect)	Select one: Input, Output, Outcome, long-term impact
Type (Effect)	Select one: from coding table or add additional one
Direction of change	Select: Increase OR Decrease
Comment	Any comment (optional)

The next phase included the extraction of impact chains identified in the selected sources. They were coded in the individual steps from input to output, from output to outcome, from outcome to short-term impact and from short-term impact to long-term impact (see Figure 2). Each first component of a step was labelled as 'cause' and each second component of a step was labelled as 'effect' in the data set.

Figure 2 Depiction of individual steps

The extracted information was arranged in a spreadsheet in which each row represents a single “step” between two components which contains each element of the data extraction fiche displayed in Table 4. With regards to the *Activity*, the predefined Open Science areas were used (Table 5). To link the steps identified with the relevant impact areas, the set of codes describing impacts displayed in Table 6 was used. These were based on the impact dimensions used in other Work Packages of PathOS and slightly updated in the process of coding. To increase clarity, it was also necessary to add codes for the outputs, which were not predefined as such by PathOS. The respective codes for the output component were added throughout this process, including in particular:

- Availability of Open Platforms (e.g., data sharing platforms)
- Availability of Open/FAIR data
- Number of people participating in CS
- Availability of Open Publications

Table 5 Codes for activities: Open Science areas

Activity type	Code
Open Science	Open Access
	Open/FAIR Data

	Citizen Science
	Open Code / Software
	Open Methods (including infrastructures such as EOSC)
	Open Evaluation and Assessment
	Open infrastructure (EOSC)

Table 6 Codes for outcomes and impacts

Area	Code
Academic impact	Quality
	Citations
	Integrity
	Equity
	Collaboration
	Trust
	Efficiency
	Productivity
	Re-use
	Reproducibility
	Interdisciplinarity
	Novelty
Societal impact	Engagement
	Participation
	Education and awareness
	Trust
	Policy and governance
	Empowerment
	Gender
	Diversity
	Health
	Climate/Environment
	COVID-19
	SDGs (generic)
	Better re-use and absorption of academic knowledge by societal actors
	Equity
	Privacy/ethics
Economic impact	Economic impact
	Financial/monetary impact
	Costs
	Collaboration
	Input-output
	Return on investment
	Patenting
	Innovation
	Productivity
	Cost savings
	Higher re-use and absorption of academic knowledge by economic actors
	Science-industry collaboration
	Financial savings and efficiency gains
Labour market impacts	

Area	Code
	Socially relevant products and processes
	Uptake of research results by industry

The initial allocation of codes to an impact are (societal, economic, academic) followed the usage within other Work Packages of PathOS. Several types of impact may be present across the areas of academic, societal, economic impact. For example, equity and trust are listed in the list as both academic and societal impact. Collaboration appears both as an academic and economic impact.

3.3. Data summary

Following the screening of sources and coding of information, the dataset comprises information stemming from a total of 43 unique sources. The ELIXIR case study and the scoping review are considered individual sources. Additionally, each article extracted from the scoping review literature is treated as an individual source (Table 7).

Table 7 Inclusion of sources from scoping review

Scoping review category	Total screened	Total in data set
Academic Impact literature (CS)	30	16
Societal impact literature (CS)	30	12
Academic Impact literature (OA)	27	13
ELIXIR Case study	1	1
Scoping review	1	1
Total	89	43

In total, the screening and coding exercise across the 43 sources resulted in the identification of 315 individual steps. These were found from Activity to Output (n=94), Output to Outcome (n=126), Outcome to Short-term Impact (n=52), and Short-Term Impact to Long-Term Impact (n=22).

In addition, several horizontal and other connections were found and coded. This part contained connections between Outcome and Outcome (n=6), Outcome and Long-Term Impact (n=10), Short-Term Impact and Short-Term Impact (n=4), and Long-Term Impact and Long-Term impact (n=1). Horizontal connections represent correlations between different effects (e.g., outcomes, impacts) which co-occur together.

The coding found a total of 89 individual short-term and long-term impacts. These were distributed over 23 different codes spanning all three areas (Table 8). Several codes (highlighted with an asterisk) were introduced inductively by the study team for the lack of better options in the predefined set.

Table 8 Impact code occurrence

Code	Area ³ (A, E, S)	Impact (short term)	Impact (long term)	Total
Behavioural change*	S	3	1	4
Better re-use and absorption of academic knowledge by societal actors	S	2		2
Citations	A	1		1
Climate/Environment	S	5	10	15
Collaboration	A; E	1		1
Cost savings	E	2		2
Costs	E	1	1	2
Economic growth*	E		5	5
Efficiency	A		2	2
Empowerment	S	1		1
Equality*	S	1		1
Equity	A; S	3		3
Health	S	2	2	4
Knowledge spillover*	A; S	2		2
Labour market impact	E	2		2
Policy and governance	S	4	1	5
Productivity	A; E	4		4
Quality	A	1		1
Relevant products and Services*	E	5		5
Reproducibility	A	4		4
SDG solutions (generic)	S	11	6	17
Tax revenue*	E		5	5
Trust	A; S	1		1
Total		56	33	89

The activity of coding the information led to several learnings. Firstly, as mentioned in section 3.2, some codes were initially conceived as both academic or economic impacts and were therefore not always discrete. This is a challenge for the analysis of the information further down the line. Codes used for this exercise were applied in a deductively way, based on previous project discussions. Since they were not directly conceived to be used in an approach as used for this report, the research team had to discuss and agree about the application of codes to individual cases. For instance, the codes included both “Cost savings” and “Costs”, which may be combined in further steps. In addition, these predefined codes were covering impact areas but did not fit well for intermediary components, such as outputs, which were added by the research team as a result of this shortcoming.

³ The impact areas are: Academic (A), Economic (E), Societal (S).

3.4. Initial mapping

The data can be displayed visually as a graph. As an interim step, an overall graph of all connections in the dataset was created. **Error! Reference source not found.** represents such a n illustration of the entire dataset tools freely available online, after testing of different options.⁴ This step was purely taken to gain a better understanding of the complexity of the collected data.

The type of visualisation for this initial step was chosen because it supports a preliminary visual inspection of the data and its connections by the research team. The chart displays the density of connections and allows arranging the flow from activities to impacts, which suites the idea of identifying overarching effect chains. The visual display also reveals some apparent patterns in the data. In particular, clusters around citizen science-related interventions and effects can be identified, which are likely results of the sampling of sources.

The necessity for a reduction of complexity and zooming into the effects of individual interventions is also highlighted by this way of visualising all the connections in the data set in this figure, which is too unwieldy for identifying pathways. There are too many connections and no real sequences or chains of effects are visible. Moreover, the simple density displayed in the visuals illustrates only the *frequency of connections found in the data*. This does not necessarily signify the size, strength, or relevance of an effect, but rather the availability of evidence in the included data.

⁴ Online available tools include <https://sankeymatic.com> and <https://www.rawgraphs.io>

3.5. Recasting and explication of assumptions

The last step as described by Wilkinson et al (2021) includes the recasting and refocussing of the overall mapping towards a theory of change. For the purposes of PathOS, as explained above, we treat these refocused visualisations, starting from a specific Open Science activity, as our main chains of impact (“key impact pathways”).

The process starts with a selection of the relevant intervention.⁵ To do so practically, a sequential process was employed to identify a chain spanning from a given activity to all relevant effects emanating from this activity and its individual effects.

- 1) Identify all connections starting at a given activity and the frequency with which they lead to a certain output.
- 2) Identify all connections starting at each of these outputs and the frequency with which they lead to a certain outcome.
- 3) Identify all connections starting at each of these outcomes and the frequency with which they lead to a certain short-term impact.
- 4) Identify all connections starting at each of these short-term impacts and the frequency with which they lead to a certain short-term long-term impact.

Based on this approach, the selected connections were inserted into the same tool as used for the overall mapping introduced in the previous section.⁶ This results in an initial visual mapping of all effects that may be attributed to the given Open Science intervention.⁷ Recasting may include different means:

- Rearranging elements according to the impact chain from activity to impact
- Removal of steps and components with low frequency
- Limitation of horizontal connections
- Clustering of related codes

For instance, an impact found once in the source data as an effect of an intervention may be less relevant to for “the most important or relevant pathways” according to the definitions used by the PathOS project. These judgments required knowledge of the underlying evidence, since the frequency of occurrence in the data is not necessarily an indicator of effect size, strength, or relevance, and were therefore discussed and validated in the by different means. In the first instance, this included the team of authors. In addition, discussion among project partners, as

⁵ Other selection criteria can be used, for example a group of activities, a group of impacts, but the data can also be filtered by the type of source material such as case studies, individual papers, since they were included as variables in the data fiche.

⁶ In some cases, the closer inspection also led to the recoding of data throughout the dataset.

⁷ Examples are given in Section 4.

well as through a stakeholder workshop conducted in March 2024, guided the identification of the pathways reported in the next section.

For this deliverable, a narrative explanation of the main decisions during the recasting stage is provided. In addition, each pathway is supported by contextual information and assumptions underlying the impact chains.

4. Results

As part of this report, examples for three key impact pathways were developed, based on the selected data and covers the following areas:

- Section 4.1 introduces an impact pathway starting from Citizen Science activities.
- Section 4.2 presents a in impact pathway starting from Open Access activities.
- Section 4.3 identifies a pathway *leading* to different impacts related to the environment and climate.

The results reported in section 4.1 and 4.2 are a downstream analysis, i.e., they started with the selection of specific interventions. For the pathway displayed in section 4.3, the process was followed in reverse order in the form of an “upstream analysis” (Wilkinson et al. 2021, 98).

A note to readers before progressing to the individual pathways: the interventions displayed in the next sections are generalisations of actual activities taking place under the umbrella of Open Science. For example, when the activity mentions “Open Access”, this must be understood as the spectrum of activities which can result in an increase of Open Access publications. While the use of such-catch all terms unfortunately reduces the specificity of each pathway for now, a detailed analysis of all possible intervention under these catch-all terms would be beyond the scope of the project which focuses on the high-level impacts of a range of Open Science areas (e.g., Open Access, Citizen Science), not individual projects.⁸

The present report is a proof-of-concept and its intention must be understood in conjunction with the additional information under preparation by PathOS, such as linking the indicator handbook to the pathways, which promises more detailed descriptions related to specific impacts. In addition, more attention will be paid to better describing outputs, relevant inputs, concerned stakeholders, and the directionality of effects. Finally, the pathways are likely to be incomplete due to the selection of a snapshot of the data to inform the method. These shortcomings will be rectified by the PathOS team in the next steps outlined in Section 6.

⁸ However, learnings from the exercise and feedback from the stakeholder workshop carried out in March 2024 also pointed out that more specificity would be useful, for example covering specific interventions, inputs etc.

4.1. Pathway 1 (Citizen Science)

This pathway was constructed based on the selection of 'citizen science' as the origin point. The selection of the topic followed the selection of documents and sources in this area identified by the scoping review. Following the process outlined in Section 3, an initial mapping based on the selected data is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4 Initial mapping of Citizen Science impact chain

The mapping shows the range of effects found to occur from Citizen Science activities. Prominently, this leads to outputs such as availability of Open and FAIR data, people participating in CS projects, as well as collaboration with societal actors. Participation also features strongly, which was defined as increased societal participation of CS participants after being part of a

From the perspective of the study team, Figure 4 also includes several effects which the study team assess are less relevant in the context of citizen science impacts, because they would only occur indirectly through the availability of FAIR data. Effects in the economic realm such as creation of new companies, increase in relevant products and services, labour market impacts, and tax revenue are likely not the focus of Citizen Science projects nor always attributable to them. They also did not feature in the source documents addressing Citizen Science, but in those looking at the creation of Open/FAIR data in the context of typical research projects. Therefore, they were summarised in the eventual pathway under economic impacts following discussion among the study team.

Figure 5 presents the recast pathway. As explained above, many elements relating to economic impacts were removed by the project team. The effects illustrated in this figure are related to outputs of Citizen Science projects, in particular, availability of data, the participation of people, as well as collaborations related to the Citizen Science project. The availability of data displays connections with academic and economic impacts, including the re-use of data, productivity, cost savings and efficiency, as well as quality. Open data also relates to reproducibility. Many of these outcomes have the potential to create economic effects. Yet, the specific evidence is limited and therefore the illustration does not draw a direct connection between the long-term economic impacts of Citizen Science.

Figure 5 further illustrates that societal effects are created indirectly through the participants experience in projects. The evidence has shown that participation and collaboration can create stronger societal participation, lead to empowerment of citizen scientists, improve education and awareness of certain issues, as well as societal engagement. These together, sometimes in correlation with the improved data quality, can lead to effects on policy and governance, if conditions permit so. Changed policy and governance can in turn lead to impact on the societal development goals at large or in more concrete areas such as health and environment. In addition, the societal outcomes of Citizen Science can give rise to an increase in trust in research.

Figure 5 Pathway for Citizen Science (Draft)

Context, assumptions, limitations

Citizen Science impacts are often societal in nature and the result of complex processes and dynamics. From the analysis of publications focussing on Citizen Science, it was possible to capture some of these contextual factors of Citizen Science which can affect the realisation of impacts. They also illustrate important underlying assumptions and potential limitations of the pathway.

A main finding concerned the quality of data resulting from Citizen Science projects. Some studies argue that data quality may be affected by demographic factors such as age and level of education. Therefore, in order to have a successful citizen science project, it is important that the project and the participants are aligned (Earp et al., 2020). A key factor impacting data quality is training and thus providing training to the citizens undertaking the projects can be a key for obtaining sound data (Ratnieks et al., 2016). Yet other studies found no significant quality discrepancy between data collected by citizens or by experts (see e.g. Crall et al., 2011).

Clear benefits can be found for the participating citizens: participating did not only positively impact the participants' knowledge and attitude towards science (Bruckermann et al., 2021), but it improved also their soft skills such as communication, as well as argumentation and critical thinking skills (Araujo et al., 2022). Furthermore, participation in Citizen Science projects provoked "a desire to make a difference" (Walker et al., 2021), a feeling of satisfaction and enjoyment in the participants for contributing to science.

Yet, there are a number of aspects that limit the potential effects. Some projects may experience accessibility issues due to the way in which they are planned and conducted. For instance, if they require physical tasks or intensive activities, this may limit participation (Earp et al., 2020). Additional factors potentially hindering participation in CS projects are linked to geographic and social bias which may occur due to CS projects being mostly carried out in North America or Europe and in which participants are middle-class and have access to education. In addition, another potential limiting factor of CS is the frequent requirement of using technological tools, which are not always available to all members of the society (Walker et al., 2021).

Participants' motivation can also be a challenge to the scientists in the project, namely to maintain the motivation of the volunteers to continue contributing to the project. Feedback and social recognition were found to play a pivotal role in keeping the interest and motivation high. The greater they are, the more participants are inclined to contribute to CS (Earp et al., 2020).

In terms of challenges, achieving policy and governance impact represents a major one; while there is evidence of CS having an impact at local and regional levels, and being used as an instrument for monitoring environmental and health related issues, evidence of CS impact at national and international levels is limited (Klebel et al. 2023). One reason for this is may be the difficulty in acknowledging CS data as scientific evidence by policymakers (Mahajan et al., 2022).

It should also be mentioned that implementing Citizen Science projects can be associated with potential risks. One type of such risks are health and safety risks to participants arising from CS. Several studies highlighted that projects might expose participants to dangerous situations, for instance, while collecting data on floods (Walker et al., 2021). In addition, Citizen science projects often encompass the use of technological tools which may contain personal information of the participants, and which must be treated carefully (Walker et al., 2021). This , ill-designed projects may threaten the privacy of participants' data.

4.2. Pathway 2 (Open Access)

This pathway was constructed based on the selection of 'Open Access' as the origin point. The selection of the topic was based on the purpose of the report to serve as proof-of-concept and the selection of source documents. Following the process outlined in Section 3, an initial mapping is shown in Figure 6.

The mapping is based on a limited numbers of sources that were included following the data screening procedure. Clear links from Open Access-related intervention connect to outputs such as the actual availability of publications in Open Access, which in turn has been found to affect citations.

Further downstream to the impacts of Open Access, effects in the academic realm such as reproducibility, quality, collaboration, productivity, and others are visualised. This is likely a result of the sampling, which was based on documents related to the academic impact of Open Access publications.

Figure 6 Initial mapping of Open Access impact chain.

The next step conducted by the research team was the re-casting of the mapping into a pathway framework. Given the limitations outlined above, this was a difficult exercise and the preliminary result is displayed in Figure 7. The decision was made to focus on the outcomes resulting from Open Access publications. Better re-use of knowledge by other actors was connected to generic potential impacts at societal and economic level, which is introduced as a placeholder in this figure. Concerning effects accruing in academia, it was decided to keep the outcomes of novelty and citations and highlight their connection to academic impacts, displayed in yellow. These academic impacts relate on the other hand to potential impacts on the economy (e.g., through increased productivity, efficiency, and reproducibility) and, potentially, the achievement of a broad range of sustainable development goals.

An important question is the location of reproducibility as an impact or whether it in fact creates further impacts such as quality, efficiency, and productivity. The chosen visualisation is a pragmatic decision to display these aspects at the same level, acknowledging that the effects cannot easily be displayed a linear model.

Figure 7 Pathway for Open Access (Draft)

The mapping and the resulting pathway for Open Access are, in the perspective of the project team, in need of additional data and more serious recasting, as well as introducing more specific codes for all stages. Only a limited number of publications was included in the creation of this pathway. Therefore, the pathway in its current shape is likely too simple. At the output stage, for example, it currently considers only the catch-all term publications, which should be specified in further research. Alternatives could be introducing journal articles, preprints, and books as specific outputs of Open Access interventions.

In addition, the question of costs is entirely missing from the visualisation. This topic was addressed in the source data. However, it is not certain, and indeed hotly debated, if the widespread adoption of Open Access is leading to cost savings or increases. Since there is little reliable evidence whether there are indeed cost savings, this was not coded as such by the project team. Introducing more contextual information related to Open Access, including the required *inputs*, such as financial means for Article Processing Charges, will be crucial to address this evident shortcoming.

Context, assumptions, limitations

Limitations are also evident to when it relates to rather well-known aspects of Open Access and its effects. For example, several studies reported on citation advantages of OA, showing that both a negative and positive correlation between OA and citations can be found (Fahimifar et al, 2022). Holmberg et al. (2020) illustrate significant disciplinary and platform-specific differences in the advantage conferred by OA, with certain fields experiencing increased citations and social media attention for OA articles, while others show the opposite trend, as seen in medicine and health sciences. This variability underscores the need to acknowledge the influence of disciplinary contexts when assessing the impact of OA on citation rates. Since the effect of OA on citation rates varies across disciplines, a general key impact pathway of OA on citations may not be universally applicable.

Moreover, variations between different types of OA, such as Gold, Bronze, and Hybrid models, present another layer of complexity in understanding the effects of OA. Chen et al. (2021) evaluated different OA categories separately and found citation advantages associated with specific “colours” of OA. However, due to the diverse outcomes across OA models, a generalized key impact pathway of OA on citation rates may not capture these nuances accurately. Therefore, it’s essential to consider the specific OA model when assessing its impact on citation rates, and a one-size-fits-all approach may not be appropriate.

Lastly, studies like McCabe and Snyder’s (2021) investigate the “Matthew effect” related to OA and introduce complexities that may not always align with a linear display as used in the key impact pathway analysis. The presence of a “Matthew effect” demonstrates nuanced dynamics in citation patterns upon opening access to academic articles, highlighting differential impacts on citations for articles of varying quality levels. These aspects do not easily fit into a generalized key impact pathway of OA due to their nuanced nature and the need for context-specific

considerations. Thus, although these insights contribute to our understanding of OA's impact, they may not easily translate into a standardized key impact pathway.

In terms of benefits, several articles highlighted benefits such as wider readership for novelty, for instance Tang et al. (2017) highlight how OA can facilitate the dissemination of research findings, making them more accessible to diverse stakeholders and communities. This increased accessibility aligns with the broader objectives of the SDGs, particularly those related to education (SDG 4), health (SDG 3), gender equality (SDG 5), and environmental sustainability (SDG 13). By enhancing the availability of scholarly information, OA contributes to advancing knowledge and innovation, ultimately supporting efforts towards achieving the SDGs. Therefore, recognizing the potential positive impacts of OA on SDG-related outcomes adds another dimension to understanding its broader societal benefits. However, it's important to acknowledge that while OA may have the potential to contribute to the SDGs, its actual impact in achieving these goals may vary depending on various contextual factors and implementation strategies.

4.3. Pathway 3 (Impact on climate and environment)

The third pathway differs from the other two by being an “upstream analysis”. The intention behind including this approach was to test whether starting the selection from a given impact, in this case those coded as “climate/environment”, will yield an overview of the individual steps and effects leading up to this type of impact.

Figure 8 displays the initial mapping resulting of this exercise. Starting from the impact “climate/environment”, all preceding steps were identified. Policy and governance and behavioural change are identified factors affecting this impact. Equity also featured in the data as an outcome which can lead to the specific impact. Move one step further, the mapping displays a strong connection between elements such as education and awareness, participation, engagement, and societal collaborations, which emanate from citizen science. In addition, the availability of FAIR/Open data was found to connect to quality and empowerment, which connects to policy and governance.

The findings illustrate the important mediating factor of policy and governance, which can be affected by a broad range of societal aspects. In addition, the availability of data, such as collected through citizen science projects, can improve quality of decision-making, through better monitoring systems, but also empower societal actors to use such data to improve policy making. In this initial mapping, the nature of the underlying data, stemming largely from documents addressing citizen science, is again evident.

Figure 8 Initial mapping of effects leading to climate/environmental impact

These aspects were taken into consideration for the visual display of the impact chain for Climate/Environment displayed in Figure 9. Firstly, the impact on climate and environment is displayed as a long-term effect, which is largely mediated through short-term impacts on policy and governance, as well as behavioural change. These, in turn, are affected by the quality of available data and research, as well as through societal processes and factors. For this purpose, the codes of participation, empowerment, engagement, and education and awareness are clustered together, due to the proximity of the concepts and difficulty in isolating their effects at this level. Equity was found to have a link to policy and governance and to climate and environment, respectively. However, the causal relationship of the concept of equity to these impacts is likely complex and is therefore displayed with dashed lines.

Figure 9 Pathway for Impact on Climate and Environment (draft)

The formulation of this pathway followed a different approach than the previous two which requires careful reflection and interpretation. In addition, the underlying sampling bias towards citizen science activities appears in the visualisation.

The screening of the literature showed that Open Science, and in particular Citizen Science, could lead to impacts on Climate and Environment, particularly on biodiversity, pollution, conservation etc... Yet, specific limitations relate to the question of direct and potential impacts, as well as the mediating role of policy and governance.

For example, several studies found evidence of direct impacts of involvement of participants in CS activities on the environment. CS enhanced participants' understanding of environmental topics and prompted the adoption of more environmentally-friendly behaviour (Santori et al., 2021). In particular, it was possible to notice a positive impact on participants' attitude towards animals, nature and biodiversity (Kelemen-Finan et al., 2018).

In addition, it was found that CS increased availability of data, hence contributing to better monitoring and understanding of environmental issues. This, in turns, influenced engagement with policy making, thereby potentially affecting environment in long-term. For instance, Brooks et al. (2019) reported that a CS project was observed to complement the work of the public authorities, resulting in enhanced governmental monitoring of pollution, and enforcement of sanctions.

However, engaging with policymaking poses also challenges, as documented by Dhillon (2017) who found that CS activities boosted empowerment and community building, but encountered difficulties in influencing political decision-making, hence leading to limited impacts on policy making procedures.

In addition, as with the impact of CS displayed in the first pathway, the quality of data collected through CS projects, as well as the impact of participants is dependent on enabling factors such as training.

5. Impact pathways and causality

Studying the causal effects of Open Science practices is a challenging exercise. Within PathOS, this aspect is acknowledged in different tasks. The D1.2 Scoping Review (Klebel et al., 2024), it already highlighted that many of the screened academic studies did not support causal claims due to their study design. In addition, D1.2 emphasised that the role of confounding variables, due to data or conceptual issues, is difficult to assess and that effects and their size and strength are complicated to measure. It also found a risk of being subject to a "streetlight effect", that is a specific observational bias related to the availability of data.

It must be expected that the identified pathways incorporate reflect similar problems, for example towards desired results of specific practices, based on the available and eventually selected evidence. For example, the underlying scoping review focused on the presence of

evidence in the literature. However, the absence of evidence found in the literature does not mean that there is an absence of other effects – although this may be difficult to measure and find suitable evidence for. Neither does a surmounting presence of a given effect in the literature mean that such an effect has a stronger effect than other areas only covered by fewer studies. In addition, evidence for more recent practices may not yet have been available due to time-lags of scientific publications as well as lack of evaluation reports for recent Open Science policy programmes and projects.

Negative effects as well as confounding variables and effects are not necessarily represented in the impact chains either. Yet it is good practice to anticipate and explicate them during an intervention design, if not trying to find a remedy through the intervention design themselves. In PathOS, these are intended to be addressed through the contextual information provided for each pathway. This may also be part of a cost-benefit analysis, which other strands of PathOS are developing (Delugas et al., 2023).

In addition, Open Science is an umbrella term. The causal mechanism between the open availability of a data set and its re-use differs from the causal mechanism of a citizen project leading to changes in policy and governance and by extension health and the environment. For example, the impact of open access on policy may be constructed as the effect of the openness of articles on policymaking at large. Yet, the science-policy interface has been researched in many different contexts and those results show that different mechanisms are at play translating research results into policy (see e.g., Nelson et al. 2023). Developing a theoretically coherent concept for all individual causal mechanisms is out of the scope of the PathOS project. Yet, seeing the impact pathways as structural causal models (Klebel and Traag, 2024), without always implying the type and strength of effect, allows generalising the findings to a certain extent.

A further challenge derived from the approach taken in this derivable is the “cumulative” step in the identification of the impact pathways. By grouping effects from different sources under similar codes, the causal effect that may be identifiable in one case is not necessarily the same as in the next case with the same code and components. This level of granularity is lost with the design of the pathways and is a result of a trade-off between providing overarching pathways which showcase (evidence-based) possibilities of impacts of Open Science and case-by-case impact chains with more detailed and reliable causal claims, even though the evidence for finding population-level impacts outside the sphere of control of individual interventions and their beneficiaries is always challenging.

With the intention to illustrate several key pathways to impacts of different Open Science interventions, this trade-off is taken by the PathOS project. The alternative would be to not have higher-level impact pathways that group and cumulate impacts at all. In practice, the step of simplifying the findings into pathways shown in Section 3 also includes a decision on reducing

the total amount of components and steps in the individual pathways in through the judgements by the project team and the validation with stakeholders. The proof-of-concept approach for this report provides valuable lessons learnt to improve the process and underlying information.

The various results of PathOS are increasingly pointing to the need for more empirical studies with study designs addressing causal effects. PathOS aims to inspire such studies in the context of the project's case studies. It is also the intention of PathOS to inspire future academic research as well as practical studies, for example impact assessments and evaluations in a policy context, by identifying gaps of evidence or causal understanding of the effects of Open Science practices and resources.

6. Lessons learnt and next steps

6.1. Lessons learnt

This deliverable set out as a proof-of-concept of the stepwise approach to identify Key Impact Pathways of Open Science. As shown in the previous sections, the results show that the approach works in principle and can be scaled up and improved by using additional sources of evidence during the process. This will allow the identification of additional pathways and the refinement of the existing ones.

The results show not just the possibility to trace the effects of different Open Science interventions up to the impact stage ("downstream analysis"). They also demonstrate the potential of this approach to identify the activities that may create certain academic, societal, and economic impacts ("upstream analysis").

As noted comprehensively in the previous sections, this should always be done cautiously and must be contextualised. Therefore, the pathways should be accompanied by contextual information which describes limitations and underlying assumptions.

The research team also encountered challenges while conducting the research and derived a set of valuable lessons learnt to inform the next steps:

- The codes developed by the PathOS project could in principle be used in a deductive manner. Yet, they were mainly intended as impact areas and require attention when being applied in an impact chain. A pragmatic solution during the course of the research was to explicitly add output-level codes which can be linked in the future to the indicator handbook. Further attention will be paid to streamline and merge or redefine codes where appropriate.
- The usage of catch-all codes for interventions limits applicability for specific interventions. As explained, this will remain a trade-off between the objectives of the

PathOS project and the intended usage of the impact pathways in the future. Steps to address this shortcoming will include the better coverage of intervention in the selection of sources, a stronger focus on inputs, as well as more fine-grained outputs.

- The research team has coded several horizontal connections, which are interpreted as components (e.g., outcomes, impacts), which correlate with each other. These add complexity to the picture, which must be acknowledged in the contextual information eventually produced for each pathway.
- The formulation of pathways as described in section 4 was an exercise which requires expert judgment and cannot be fully automated. While it could be possible to assign weights to variables such as the type and strength of evidence, such a step would in itself require the classification and quantification of different types of evidence and a judgment of the value of such weights. The mix of automated and manual analysis proved possible and will therefore be continued, with specific attention to use co-creation methods to develop and validate the results and enrich their context.
- Valuable information was contained in documents and academic literature which were not included in the analysis, due to a lack of identifiable impact chain. This includes, for instance the information on training of Citizen Science participants or the differences in impact of differences Open Access colours. Such documents were flagged by the research team and not fully discarded but revisited to inform the contextual information provided with a pathway.

6.2. Next steps

As a proof-of-concept, the deliverable informs the next steps of the work within the PathOS project. This concerns firstly the extraction and coding of additional information from the literature review and the project's six case studies. The objective of this step is to refine the identified pathways and to identify additional ones. Second, the data extraction fiche will be updated and better tuned to the output component. Third, we will enrich the pathways with other results from the project, in particular indicators. Finally, the presentation, with contextual information in a standardised template, validated by project partners and stakeholders, will wrap up the activities.

Concerning the extraction and coding of additional information, the literature database underlying the scoping review provides clear next steps. Some 300 papers remain unscreened in the areas of Citizen Science and Open Access. In addition, some 90 papers remain tagged to the areas of general Open Science, Open Code, Open Evaluation, Open Methods, and Open/FAIR data (Table 9). In the next step, the 90 papers covering areas not addressed so far will be prioritised. Concerning Open Access and Citizen Science, additional papers will be screened to verify whether the codes and resulting impact chains are already saturated and to ensure that other practices are better covered, such Open Access books. In addition, specific

attention will be given to relevant non-academic grey literature, such as policy and programme evaluations and impact assessments.

Only a limited number of studies were found to provide evidence of impact according to the selection criteria used by PathOS. It might thus be difficult to produce “downstream” pathways for areas such as open code, open methods, or open evaluation. This will be tested in the next steps.

Table 9 Overview of screened and unscreened literature

	General	Citizen Science	Open Access	Open Code	Open Evaluation	Open Methods	Open-FAIR data
Academic	0 (14)	30 (63)	27 (190)	0 (6)	0 (8)	0 (2)	0 (29)
Societal	0 (2)	30 (137)	0 (14)	0 (2)	n/a	n/a	n/a
Economic	0 (3)	n/a	0 (5)	n/a	0 (1)	n/a	0 (4)

- = potentially minor increase (300 remaining)
- = not applicable
- = to code in next steps (90 remaining)

In addition, five out of the six PathOS case studies have not yet been included. The experience gained through the Elixir case study shows that having the case study mapped onto an intervention logic framework prior to encoding it is very efficient. Therefore, additional efforts will be made to support the development of intervention logics for each case study and subsequently including them in the data.

Concerning the data extraction fiche, the work done by the study team and the input received during the March 2024 stakeholder workshop point to important updates relating to the context of interventions and impacts. To better capture this information, future activities will address inputs, stakeholders, as well as the type and strength of evidence. An overview of these variables is provided in Table 10.

Table 10 Proposed updates for data extraction fiche

Additional information	Definition
Inputs (Cause)	Add inputs where mentioned or can be inferred from source (for activity only) (optional)
Stakeholders	Select one or more from coding table (optional)
Related indicator	Add indicator name where available, e.g. in case study file (optional)
Type of evidence	From scoping review: E.g., modelling, experimental, qualitative, quantitative, other (optional)
Strength of evidence	from scoping review: Assessment of strength of evidence (optional)

More attention will also be paid to the output stage, where the lessons learnt, and new codes reported in Section 3.2 will be included. The instructions used by the research team to code the information will be updated accordingly. A preliminarily updated data extraction fiche is available Annex I.

Concerning the enriching of the impact pathways, the updated fiche already contains a field for related indicators which will apply to all related steps, where available. In addition, this aspect can be addressed through project-internal co-creation activities between the research teams working on the indicator handbooks and the research teams working on the impact pathways.

Finally, presenting the pathways requires making explicit contextual information and underlying assumptions. Through the updates relating to the data extraction fiche, more information about the underlying evidence, stakeholders concerned will be systematically collected. A comprehensive summary and explanation of each impact pathway will be produced by the project. This may be done through collaborative exercises within the PathOS project. A proposed template for the final Key Impact Pathways of PathOS is included in Annex II.

An updated version of the deliverable D1.3 will be produced by June 2025. The structure of the updated deliverable can be found below.

Box 1 Draft structure of updated deliverable

- Introduction
- Methodology and Process
- Data Summary: Updated Numbers and Additional Detailed Data
- Results & Pathways
 - Differentiation Between Mature and Emerging Pathways
 - Presentation of 3-5 Mature Pathways
 - Presentation of 3-5 Emerging Pathways
- Discussion
 - Discussion on causal effects of Open Science
 - Implications for Synthesis of PathOS results in D1.4
- Conclusions
- Annexes
 - Templates
 - Codes and Definitions
 - Additional Information on Data
 - Additional Information on Pathways (if required)

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Annex I: Updated data extraction fiche

Following the lessons learnt, the data extraction fiche for next activities will be updated with the introduction of additional information (*highlighted in italics*).

Topic area	Field/variable	Explanation
Admin info	Source	Name of case study OR id of paper OR D1.2 chapter
	Type of source	Case study OR scoping review OR literature
	When	Date on which the information was entered
	Who	Name or initials of coder(s)
Input data	Quote or text	Copy of relevant text (e.g., "key findings" from data charting), where feasible
	Description of logic	Short description of impact chain (optional)
Cause	Step (Cause)	Select one: Activity, Output, Outcome, short term Impact, long term impact
	Type (Cause)	Select one: from coding table or add additional one
	<i>Inputs (Cause)</i>	<i>Add inputs where mentioned or can be inferred with little room for doubt (for activity only)</i>
Effect	Step (Effect)	Select one: Output, Outcome, Short-term Impact, long-term impact
	Type (Effect)	Select one: from coding table
Additional information	Direction of change	Select: Increase OR Decrease
	<i>Stakeholders</i>	<i>Select one or more from coding table (optional)</i>
	<i>Related indicator</i>	<i>Add indicator name where available, e.g. in case study file (optional)</i>
	<i>Type of evidence</i>	<i>From scoping review: E.g., modelling, experimental, qualitative, quantitative, other (optional)</i>
	<i>Strenght of evidence</i>	<i>from scoping review: Assessment of strength of evidence (optional)</i>
	Comment	Any comment

Annex II: Proposed Key Impact Pathway Fiche

Based on the lessons learnt with the activities drafting this report, the final impact pathways are intended to feature the following information.

[TITLE]
[Short description]

Visual representation

```

graph LR
    subgraph Headers
        direction LR
        H1[Activity]
        H2[Output]
        H3[Outcome]
        H4[Short-term impact]
        H5[Long-term impact]
    end
    A[Activity A] --> O[Output A]
    O --> Out[Outcome A]
    Out --> ST1[Short-term impact A]
    Out --> ST2[Short-term impact A]
    ST1 --> LT1[Long-term impact A]
    ST2 --> LT2[Long-term impact B]
    
```

Economic
Academic
Societal

Context and relevant inputs
[text]

Underlying assumptions and limitations
[Text]

List of elements

Step	Type	Related metric (indicator handbook)
Activity		
Output		
Outcome		
Short-term impact		
Long-term impact		

Further reading / example literature
[list of relevant texts]